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ABSTRACT

FMCG companies use green marketing as a tool to deal with environmental issues. Consumers have become more concerned about the green product, green production process, source of natural materials, eco-friendly packaging, and recycling of waste nowadays. Hence, the FMCG firms turned towards green marketing. This study aims to bring out the significance of green marketing and how FMCG companies can make it an opportunity to stand out and gain an advantage over their rivalry. The adoption of green marketing in every aspect of the marketing mix is a challenge. From this conceptual study, we can understand that the green marketing of firms meets with sustainable development. FMCG companies improve their brand image with the help of green marketing. The study critically reviews the consumers' awareness and attitude concerning eco-friendly products' purchase decisions. The article reveals the green marketing strategies adopted and implemented by FMCG companies to increase brand equity.

Introduction

Green marketing is the concept of marketing eco-friendly products to the consumer. Consumers are becoming more aware of eco-friendly products. Promoting eco-friendly products concerning environmental benefits Green products are positioned in consumers' minds as safe for the environment and human health. Green companies' marketing shows ecological responsibility. This article explores and investigates marketing adoption by FMCG companies in India. FMCG companies do green marketing in packed food & beverages, non-durable household products, and personal care products. The FMCG companies promote their brand through green marketing. Adoption of green marketing by FMCG companies increase the brand image and value

Objectives:

- ❖ To explore the adoption of green marketing by some FMCG companies in India
- ❖ To know the significance of green marketing
- ❖ To understand the relation between green marketing and brand equity
- ❖ To identify the challenges in the adoption of green marketing

Research methodology

This article is a conceptual study of green marketing and its relation with brand building, which enhances the brand equity of the FMCG companies. The top players of the FMCG sectors who have adopted green marketing practices are studied. The secondary data have been collected from various research articles, journals, and websites to carry this theoretical research. The sustainability reports of the FMCG companies also used in this article. These reports are collected from the various FMCG company's websites.

Review of Literature:

(Amoako et al., 2020) studied the green marketing and purchase behavior of the people. Their study inferred that green marketing has a significant influence on purchase intention. The companies that advertise green marketing practices are their products are preferred during purchase decisions. Price is an essential factor that mediates and moderates the association between green marketing and purchasing behavior. The cost caused by the adoption of green marketing can be compensated for building brand loyalty.

(Jayakanth & Rajesh, 2019) studied the impact of green marketing practices on customer satisfaction. Conclusion This study finding reveals that the determination of eco-friendly products is the primary factor in green marketing practices. Green products awareness, environmental deterioration has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction. Pricing of an eco-friendly product plays a moderate role in green marketing practices.

(Garg & Sharma, 2017) investigated green marketing and its significant role in sustainable development. The firms should do green marketing to meet consumers' needs and wants without affecting the limited natural resources. Consumers' interest in the environment developed a concept green lifestyle. They concluded that adoption of green marketing is a costly process, but it gives a return in the long run.

(Sohail, 2017) studied the green marketing mix and its influence on the brand equity of the firms. He concluded that green products and green places were significantly associated with brand loyalty. He recommends that firms focus on the green marketing mix's product and distribution channel to increase brand loyalty. Marketers should justify the high premium price of green products in the promotion by portraying the ecological benefits.

(Saini, 2014) concluded that firms market the products should make the consumer aware of the significance of a clean and green environment. Green companies' marketing leads to an increase in price, so consumers have to be convinced by the marketer to pay a green marketing premium. Firms' recycling of plastic and waste generation reduction have to be strictly followed to make an eco-friendly environment.

Green marketing

According to the American Marketing Association, "green marketing is the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe." Green marketing implements and adopts sustainable business practices in the product, production, pricing, distribution, promotion, and packaging. Green marketing begins with the procurement of raw materials for the final product. The source of a product should be eco-friendly and nature-based. To ensure that they go along with sustainable development, firms have to adopt sustainable practices in production and processing units. They have to reduce the usage of energy consumption and waste generation. Reverse logistics is used to make adequate green packaging by collecting and recycling the post-consumer plastic waste. The firms promote their brands as environment-friendly by informing their consumers about sustainable practices.

Adoption of Green Marketing Practices by FMCG Companies

Green marketing adoption is a cost and time-consuming process. It requires enormous investment for green product manufacturing and eco-friendly packaging. In recent days, the firms have promoted to make their consumers aware of green and sustainable practices through mass media, print media, and social media. The firm's advertisement creates a good image of the brand. The tabular column illustrates the green marketing practices done by the major market players in the FMCG sector.

FMCG company	Product / Production	Packaging
<p>Hindustan Unilever limited</p>	<p>100% of electricity is derived from renewable sources.</p> <p>Carbon dioxide emission reduced 91% per ton in 2020 against the 2008 baseline.</p>	<p>Collected 1,16,000 tons of post-consumer used plastic waste in 2021.</p> <p>75,000 tons of post-consumer-use plastic is recycled, which is over 10% of HUL's plastic footprint in packaging.</p>
<p>Dabur Ltd</p>	<p>85 kW solar power plant installed in 2020.</p> <p>11,528 tons of waste recycled by Dabur manufacturing sites in 2020-2021.</p> <p>In 2020-21 Dabur had 6977 acres of land under herb and medicinal plants cultivation.</p>	<p>11,413 tons of post-consumer-use plastic waste is recycled.</p> <p>My 10kG plastic scheme is introduced for Dabur employees through the mobile app for the collection of plastic waste and rewarded with redeem points.</p> <p>In 2020-21, 12,946 kgs of plastic were collected in</p>

In 2020 - 21, 25 % of the electricity used in Britannia manufacturing facilities came from renewable sources

In 2020-21 Britannia avoided 4,50,000 kgs of plastic trays Virgin plastic consumption in secondary bags was reduced by 25%, which is equivalent to 3,50,000 kgs of plastic

- Britannia received certification of the fully recyclable laminate film under IS 14534:2016 by CIPET (central institute of petrochemicals Engg & Tech)

Marico limited

Marico achieved 100% renewable energy in the Perundurai unit, reducing 1700 tons of carbon dioxide emissions.

80% reduction in fossil fuel compared to 2012-13.

32% reduction in energy usage.

74% of energy is from renewablesources.

54 % reduction in Greenhouse gas emission intensity.

20% reduction in water consumption

7,73,000 kg of post- consumer plastic waste are collected

	Colgate Palmolive India limited	The amount of waste per ton of production sent to landfills is reduced by 82% in 2020 In 2020, Colgate reduced water use per ton of production by nearly 52 % compared to 2002 Colgate reduced water use by around 900 billion liters	Colgate planned to introduce recyclable tubes in toothpaste packages by reducing aluminum usage
	Consumer Products Ltd. Godrej consumer products limited	In 2021, Godrej reduced energy consumption by 31% In 2021, It increased its renewable energy portfolio to 30% In 2021, a 41% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions	

Source : Sustainability report of 7 FMCG companies from the company's websites

Challenges in green marketing

In green marketing, they have to ensure the source of products is eco-friendly and natural, which increases the cost of procuring raw material. Reducing conventional energy usage and shifting over to renewable energy needs enormous investment to install and recruit professional and skilled laborers. They have to organize and train the team to collect the plastic waste. Reducing virgin plastic use in packaging and recycling plastic waste is time-consuming. The reuse of plastic waste in packaging makes the package look dull. The consumer who is price conscious may prefer other products since they cannot pay the eco-friendly premium.

Green marketing and Brand equity

Green marketing is the approach to meet the demands of niche market consumers concerned about environment safe. Green marketing adoption by FMCG companies results in positioning that their brands are eco-friendly, environmentally responsible, and creates a good brand image. The niche green market has a loyal green consumer, enhancing brand loyalty. Environment benefits about the products are used in sales promotion and marketing communication. The consumer is associated with the particular brand due to this promotion, and it brings out brand recognition and brand recall.

Conclusion

Nowadays, green marketing is emerging as a new trend, and it has significance among green consumers. In this Internet era, consumers are conscious about every information, so they search about the products, whether eco-friendly or nature-based. FMCG companies are taking this opportunity to adopt green marketing to satisfy the need of green consumers. Beyond challenges in the green marketing shift, there is some competitive advantage for the marketers who produce and promote green products. FMCG companies should target and attract the youth population of India since they are more in numbers. The youth have to be informed about the eco-friendly product. The process of green marketing by FMCG companies creates a good brand image and brand loyalty. The adoption of green marketing strengthens the brand equity of the FMCG companies.

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